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LINGUISTIC BARRIERS AND ETHICAL PROBLEMS OF SIMULTANEOUS TRANSLATION

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Abstract: This article explores the challenges posed by linguistic barriers and ethical dilemmas inherent in simultaneous translation. It examines the potential for misinterpretations and inaccuracies arising from semantic and cultural differences, highlighting how such discrepancies can impact communication and potentially lead to misunderstandings, offense, or even harm. The article further analyzes the ethical obligations of interpreters, including maintaining neutrality, confidentiality, and accuracy, while navigating the complex dynamics of cultural sensitivity and professional responsibility. By considering real-world examples and theoretical frameworks, the article aims to contribute to a deeper understanding of the complexities involved in simultaneous translation and its implications for effective and ethical communication across language and cultural boundaries.

Keywords: Simultaneous translation, Interpretation, Linguistic Barriers, Cultural differences, Communication, Ethics.

Linguistics owns the subfields of phonology, morphology, syntax, semantics, etc. There is a close relationship between translation and linguistics, which will be mentioned in the next semi-chapters. Linguistic theories views translation as a linguistic activity. Catford claims about translation; "Translation is the replacement of textual material in one language by equivalent textual material in another language"¹. House says: "The linguistic approach to translation incorporates the following: meaning, equivalence, shift, text purpose and analysis, and the discourse register; which can be examined in the contexts of structural and functional linguistics, semantics, pragmatics correspondence, sociolinguistics and stylistics"². A translator plays the role of mediator between languages. Hence,

¹ Catford J.C., 1965: A linguistic theory of translation, London. Oxford University Press. 105 p.

² House, J., 2009: Translation: Oxford Introduction to Language Study, (ed) H.G Widdowson, Oxford University Press 122 p

translation is not only a bridge between languages, but also between different cultures. House thinks: “Translation mediates between languages, societies and literature, and it is through translation that linguistic and cultural barriers may be overcome”.

Synchronous translation is very difficult between the languages whose grammatical structures, particularly word orders are quite diverse. As we know, the predicate comes after subject in English, though predicate usually appears at the end of the sentence in the Azerbaijani language. So, it will be relatively easier to translate from English into Azerbaijani, however this rule is not the same while translating from Azerbaijani into English. As the predicate is at the end of the sentence, the translator has to have the ability to approximate what verb could be used before the verb is uttered. But there is not such a complicated issue in the languages whose word orders are the same. For instance, as French and English have the identical word order, there won't be any hardship in translation process. The only difference is that most adjectives come after the noun in French while the adjectives in English appear before the noun. Babayev Javid brings the difficulty of the translation into notice: “As the architect imagines the design of a building prior to its construction, a translator or an interpreter should imagine the grammatical structure of the language while translating something”³.

In learning process of simultaneous translation, translator face many linguistic barriers, such as vocabulary gaps, structural references, cultural barriers, accents and dialects and others. For example: **vocabulary gaps**, in simultaneous translation, lexical gaps provide a serious challenge since translators may come across technical or unusual terms that they are unable to translate. This may cause mistakes, omissions, or delays in the final writing.

In simultaneous translation, some instances of vocabulary gaps include: English to other languages

- Interpreting **scientific** or **technical** terms—like “**blockchain**” or “**artificial intelligence**”—that have no direct translations into other languages.

Translation of English-speaking countries' unique cultural concepts or idioms, like “**rule of thumb**” or “**black Friday**”.

- Interpreting colloquialisms or slang that translators who are not native English speakers might not understand.

Other languages to English:

- Translating ancient or historical terms from languages with long written traditions, such as Sanskrit or Latin.

Translating specialized vocabulary from fields such as law, medicine, or engineering that may not be familiar to translators who do not have expertise in those areas.

- Translating words or phrases that have multiple meanings or connotations in the source language, which can make it difficult to find an appropriate equivalent in English.
- **English to Japanese:** The Japanese language often uses the English word "software" as-is (ソフトウェア, *sofutouea*) because there was no equivalent term when the concept was first introduced.
- **English to Spanish:** The English term “**whistleblower**” is difficult to translate into Spanish; often, the English term is used or a descriptive phrase like “**persona que revela actividades ilícitas**” (person who reveals illicit activities) is employed.

³ Babayev Javid. Cognitive aspects of simultaneous and consecutive interpretations. Publisher.agency: Proceedings of the 1st International Scientific Conference «Interdisciplinary Science Studies» (January 19-20, 2023).Dublin, Ireland, 2023. 144 p.

- **English to Arabic:** The English concept of “**privacy**” **does** not have an exact equivalent in Arabic. The closest term “**خصوص**” (**khusoosiya**) doesn't fully encapsulate the legal and societal nuances of privacy in the Western context.
- **English to Russian:** The word “**accountability**” can be challenging to translate into Russian. It's often described through a phrase “**подотчетность**” (**podotchetnost**) or “**ответственность**” (**otvetstvennost**), which means 'the state of being accountable or responsible,' but the term lacks the full managerial and ethical connotations present in English.
- **English to French:** The English business term “**empowerment**” often retains its English form in French business jargon. Alternatively, a descriptive phrase like “**donner du pouvoir**” (**give power**) or “**responsabiliser**” (to make responsible) is used.

Structural differences between languages pose a significant challenge in simultaneous interpreting, as interpreters must quickly restructure sentences to make sense in the target language while maintaining the speaker's original meaning and intent. These differences can affect word order, grammar, use of tenses, and the presence or absence of certain linguistic features.

Examples of Structural Differences and Their Impact on Simultaneous Interpreting:

1. Subject-Verb-Object (SVO) vs. Subject-Object-Verb (SOV):

- English follows an SVO order: "She (S) eats (V) apples (O)."
- Hindi, an SOV language, would structure the sentence as: "वह (S) सेब (O) खाती है (V)" (She apples eats).
- An interpreter must rearrange the sentence structure while interpreting between these languages to maintain grammatical coherence.

2. Tenses and Aspects:

- English has a range of tenses and aspects to express time, such as present simple, present continuous, etc.
- Chinese, for instance, relies more on context and additional time-clarifying words rather than different verb conjugations to indicate tense.
- When interpreting from English to Chinese, the interpreter must add context to convey the correct time frame.

3. Articles:

- English uses definite and indefinite articles ("the," "a," "an") to specify nouns.
- Russian lacks articles entirely, so a simultaneous interpreter must decide how to best convey specificity or generality of a noun in the target language without the use of articles.

4. Gender and Number:

- Romance languages like Spanish or French have gendered nouns and extensive verb conjugations that agree with gender and number.
- English nouns are not gendered and verbs do not agree with the noun's gender.
- An interpreter must adapt the translation to include the correct gender and number agreements that are not explicitly stated in English.

5. Compound Tenses:

- German often uses compound tenses to express the past: "Er hat gegessen" (He has eaten).
- Interpreters must be able to deconstruct and reconstruct these compound tenses appropriately when translating into languages with simpler tense structures.

6. Modality:

- English uses modal verbs (can, should, must) to express possibility, obligation, or permission.
- Modal concepts might be expressed differently in other languages, like through verb conjugations or by using different grammatical structures.
- Thus, an interpreter must translate the modal meaning accurately, which might not be a straightforward word-for-word translation.

Simultaneous interpreters must be adept at mentally performing these structural adjustments instantaneously. This requires not only fluency but also a high level of cognitive flexibility and an extensive understanding of the linguistic nuances of both the source and target languages.

Idioms and cultural allusions pose challenges to simultaneous translation because they have deeper cultural and linguistic implications than can be conveyed through literal interpretation. These idioms are typically connected to cultural tales, historical occurrences, or grammatical quirks specific to a given language group. These colloquialisms and cultural allusions could become meaningless or lose their power when translated into a different language.

Examples of Idioms and Cultural References Barriers:

1. English to Spanish:

- Idiom: **"To hit the nail on the head"** (to describe something accurately).
- Translation Challenge: A literal translation would make little sense in Spanish. A Spanish equivalent idiom would be **"dar en el clavo"**.

2. English to Chinese:

- Cultural Reference: **"Uncle Sam"** (a personification of the United States government).
- Translation Challenge: A direct translation into Chinese might be confusing without the cultural context. An explanation may be required to convey the same meaning.

3. English to French:

- Idiom: **"It's raining cats and dogs"** (it's raining very heavily).
- Translation Challenge: This idiom would be nonsensical if translated literally into French. Instead, the French equivalent is **"Il pleut des cordes"** (it's raining ropes).

4. English to Arabic:

- Idiom: **"Bite the bullet"** (to endure a painful experience with fortitude).
- Translation Challenge: There is no direct equivalent in Arabic, so it would require a descriptive translation, like **"بشجاعة الأمر تحمل"** (endure the matter bravely).

5. English to Russian:

- Cultural Reference: **"The American Dream"** (the ideal by which equality of opportunity is available to any American, allowing the highest aspirations and goals to be achieved).

- **Translation Challenge:** This concept has specific American roots, and a direct translation into Russian might not convey the full meaning. It would require additional explanation.

Simultaneous interpreters frequently have to look for comparable idioms in the target language or, in the absence of any, provide a translation that expresses the same idea. This necessitates a thorough comprehension of both languages as well as the cultures in which they are spoken. In order to guarantee that idioms and references are clear and accessible, interpreters must also remain mindful of the cultural background of their audience. This part of simultaneous translation involves both language proficiency and cultural understanding.

Language is indeed much more than a mere tool for communication; it embodies the societal norms, cultural values, and religious beliefs of its speakers. The rich tapestry of global cultures is vividly expressed through the unique characteristics of their respective languages. Each language serves as a repository of a community's heritage, and the abrupt abandonment of native tongues in favor of a single, universal language would be akin to erasing a vast cultural heritage, a priceless loss to the world's diversity.

Furthermore, the nuances of certain emotions, feelings, and detailed descriptions are often deeply embedded within a language's structure, idioms, and lexicon, making them challenging, if not impossible, to translate directly into other languages. This specificity of expression can sometimes be confined to a particular language, revealing insights into a culture's unique way of experiencing and interpreting the world. Each language thus contributes its own perspective, adding to the collective human understanding and enriching our global civilization.

Simultaneous translation, or interpreting, comes with a set of ethical challenges that professionals in the field must navigate carefully to maintain the integrity of their work and the trust of those they serve. Here are some of the key ethical issues associated with simultaneous translation:

The fundamental tenets of simultaneous translation are **accuracy and fidelity**, which pose particular difficulties for interpreters who must adjust to the linguistic and cultural quirks of the target language while still trying to represent the speaker's message as accurately as possible. The obstacles to upholding precision and authenticity are numerous, frequently necessitating the interpreter to make snap judgments regarding the most effective way to communicate meaning, tone, and intent without distorting.

Examples for accuracy and fidelity

1. **Technical and Specialized Terminology:** It can be difficult to locate the precise translations in the target language when a speaker employs highly technical or specialized terms that are unique to professions like engineering, law, or medicine. For example, when translating the medical word "myocardial infarction" from English to its precise counterpart in the target language (in this case, "**infarto de miocardio**" in Spanish), care should be taken to avoid misconceptions.
2. **Idiomatic Expressions:** Idioms have meanings that cannot be inferred from their component words and frequently have no direct translation in other languages. For instance, the audience would probably become confused if the English expression "**to kick the bucket**" was directly translated into another language. Rather, the interpreter needs to come up with an expression or a method to explain what death means in the target language.
3. **Nuances of Tone and Register:** Accurately translating the speaker's tone, whether formal, informal, sarcastic, or humorous, poses a challenge. For instance, if a speaker uses sarcasm, the interpreter must find a way to convey that tone in the target language without losing the intended irony.

4. Real-Time Constraints: The simultaneous nature of this translation work means interpreters must process and convey messages in real-time, leaving little room for reflection or consultation of reference materials. This can make it difficult to ensure accuracy when faced with complex or unfamiliar content.

Also, translator should know other elements of ethical challenges.

Confidentiality: Interpreters often deal with sensitive or private information. Maintaining the confidentiality of the information they translate is an ethical imperative.

Impartiality and Neutrality: Interpreters must remain neutral and avoid allowing personal beliefs or biases to influence their translations. They should not take sides or become advocates for either party in the communication.

Conflict of Interest: Ethical interpreters should avoid situations where personal interests might conflict with their professional duties or compromise their neutrality.

Cultural Sensitivity: Translators must be aware of and sensitive to the cultural nuances of both the source and target languages to ensure that translations are culturally appropriate and respectful.

Professionalism: Interpreters must conduct themselves in a professional manner, which includes dressing appropriately, being punctual, and showing respect for all parties involved in the translation.

In summary, simultaneous translation is a complex balancing act that necessitates a strong ethical compass in addition to linguistic expertise. The presence of linguistic obstacles including structural distinctions, colloquial idioms, and cultural allusions demands a thorough comprehension of the source and target languages in addition to the cultural contexts in which they are used. For the interpreted message to remain accurate and true, these obstacles must be removed.

Maintaining confidentiality, impartiality, and transparency are just a few of the ethical issues with simultaneous translation that are equally important to the integrity of the industry. In order to ensure that their work meets the greatest standards in the industry, interpreters must continually navigate these morally challenging waters with tact and judgment. In order to promote cross-cultural contact, simultaneous interpreters are essential. In our increasingly interconnected world, their capacity to offer ethical and accurate translating services is critical to fostering collaboration and cross-cultural understanding. Their adept handling of language difficulties and commitment to moral values greatly aid in removing obstacles to communication, building trust, and advancing inclusivity in a multicultural environment.

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